

Preparation of some Important Medicinal Compounds. Thiosemicarbazones, Thiadiazolines, 4-Thiazolidinones and 5-Arylidine Derivatives as Antibacterial and Tuberculostatic Agents

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Thiosemicarbazides (1) have been prepared by the reaction of initial amine, ammonia and carbon disulphide with ethanol (95%) and sodium chloroacetate, followed by addition of hydrazine hydrate. Benzaldehyde 4-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-3-thiosemicarbazones (2) have been prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide (1) and different aldehydes in boiling ethanol (95%). Thiosemicarbazones (2) treated with NaOH (5%) and potassium ferricyanide solution produced thiadiazolines (3). The condensation of thiosemicarbazones with mercaptoacetic acid gave 4-thiazolidinones, which further reacted with different aldehydes in presence of sodium ethoxide to produce 5-arylidine derivatives.

4-Thiazolidinones are known to possess ameobicidal, anticonvulsant, antithyroid, antibacterial and antitubercular activity. The aryl-3-alkyl-4-thiazolidinones¹⁻⁵ have been found to be most active as psychomotor anticonvulsant and barbiturate potentiating agent. The compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

R=2-Ethoxyphenyl
R'=Different aldehydes
R''=C₆H₅

Scheme 1

The semicarbazones (2) showed ir bands at 1 150 (C=S), 3 350 (NH) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The band due to C=N stretch disappeared on the formation of thiadiazolines (3). In 3, a strong tertiary amide stretch was observed around 1 320 cm⁻¹ and that due to the secondary amine shifted towards higher wavelength at 3 460 cm⁻¹. The thiazolidinones (4) exhibited bands at 1 750 (C=O) and 1 310 cm⁻¹ (4-thiazolidinone ring system), and the arylidines (5) at 1 752 (C=O) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

Microbial testing: The title compounds were tested for antibacterial and tuberculostatic activities. The result of *in vitro* antibacterial activity study of compounds 3 and 4 against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* reveals that most of them inhibit the growth of *S. aureus*. The compounds 3, 4 and 5 were tested for antibacterial activities by nutrient agar pour plate method in dimethyl formamide using solvents in various concentrations. The *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity of thiosemicarbazones and 4-thiazolidinone derivatives was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium by serial two-fold dilution method and the retardation of the growth rate studied upto six weeks at 37°.

Experimental

Elemental analysis were carried out on semimicro analyser in the Department. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer.

4-(2-Ethoxyphenyl)-3-thiosemicarbazide (1): *o*-Phenitidine (0.1 mol) in NH₄OH (25 ml) was reacted with CS₂ (10 ml), followed by sodium chloroacetate

(0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (10 ml; 50%) to yield the product, which was crystallised from 95% ethanol, (90.6%), m.p. 138° (lit.¹ 137°).

Benzaldehyde-4-(ethoxyphenyl)-3-thiosemicarbazones (2): Benzaldehyde (0.1 mol) was condensed with compound 1 (0.1 mol) in boiling ethanol (95%), and resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (95%). Using this procedure all the compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

2-Benzaldehyde-5-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-imino-1,3,4-thiadiazoline (3): Compound 2 (0.1 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (25%), and NaOH solution with little water (5 ml) added. The mixture was heated on a water-bath and aqueous 5% potassium ferricyanide added to precipitate the product, which was filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from ethanol (95%). Similarly, other compounds of the series were synthesised (Table 2).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF THIOSEMICARBAZONES (2)*

Sl. no.	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretat on zone of inhibition (µg/disk)**		Myco. antituber- culosis H ₃₇ R _v **
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	158	+	+	+
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	193	+	-	+
3.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO ₂	171	-	+	+
4.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	184	-	-	+
5.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	193	+	-	+
6.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ SO	184	-	-	+
7.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ SO	175	+	+	+
8.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ SO	210	-	-	+
9.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂	106	-	-	+
10.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂	214	-	-	+
11.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	158	+	-	+
12.	5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ SO ₂	198	+	+	+

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analyses. ** Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = <20 mm, (++) = >20 mm; tuberculostatic concentration = 0.02 µg ml⁻¹.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF 1,3,4-THIADIAZOLINES (3)*

Sl. no.	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretation zone of inhibition (µg/disk)**		Myco. antituber- culosis H ₃₇ R _v **
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ SO	167	+	++	+
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	185	-	-	+
3.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ SO ₂	155	+	+	+
4.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	125	-	-	+
5.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO ₂	182	-	+	+
6.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ SO	294	+	+	+
7.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ SO	105	+	+	+
8.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ SO	140	-	-	+
9.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ SO ₂	340	-	-	+
10.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ SO ₂	197	-	-	+
11.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO ₂	150	+	-	+
12.	5 Br-2 OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ SO ₂	170	++	-	+

* All the compounds (R=2-ethoxyphenyl) gave satisfactory C, H, N (S) analysis. ** Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = <20 mm, (++) = >20 mm; tuberculostatic concentration = 0.02 µg ml⁻¹.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (4)*

Sl. no.	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretation zone of inhibition (µg/disk)**		Myco. antituber- culosis activity H ₃₇ R _v **
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	118	+	-	+
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	152	+	+	+
3.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	138	+	-	+
4.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	200	-	-	+
5.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	168	+	+	+
6.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	175	-	-	+
7.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	194	+	-	+
8.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	121	-	-	+
9.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ SO ₂	158	-	-	+
10.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ SO ₂	144	-	-	+
11.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	230	++	++	+
12.	2-OH-5-Br-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ S ₂ O ₂	232d	++	++	+

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N (S) analysis. ** Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = <20 mm, (++) = >20 mm, tuberculostatic concentration = 0.02 µg ml⁻¹.

TABLE 4—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF 5-ARYLIDINES (5)*

Sl. no.	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretation zone of inhibition ($\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$)**		Myc. antituberculosis activity H_{27}, R_v **
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	
1.	C_6H_5	$C_{10}H_{10}N_2S_2O_4$	125	—	—	+
2.	$4.CH_3.C_6H_4$	$C_{16}H_{17}N_2S_2O_4$	162	++	+	+
3.	$2.OH.C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2O_4$	118	—	—	+
4.	$CH=CH.C_6H_5$	$C_{17}H_{17}N_2S_2O_4$	176	—	—	+
5.	$4.OCH_3.C_6H_4$	$C_{18}H_{17}N_2S_2O_4$	179	++	+	+
6.	$2.Cl.C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O_4Cl$	146	—	—	+
7.	$4.Cl.C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O_4Cl$	131	+	—	+
8.	$4.NO_2.C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{10}N_4SO_4$	199	—	—	+
9.	$3.NO_2.C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{10}N_4SO_4$	171	—	—	+
10.	$4.OH.3.OCH_3.C_6H_4$	$C_{22}H_{17}N_2S_2O_4$	201	++	+	+
11.	$2.OH.5.Br.C_6H_4$	$C_{20}H_{14}BrN_2S_2O_4$	222d	++	+	+

* All the compounds (R=2-ethoxyphenyl, R'=C₆H₅) gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analysis. ** Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = < 20 mm, (++) = > 20 mm; tuberculostatic concentration = 0.02 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

2-Phenyl-3-[(2-ethoxyphenyl)-thioureido]-4-thiazolidinone (4): Compound 2 (0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) with mercaptoacetic acid (0.12 mol) was refluxed (8 h) using Dean and Stark water-separator. After removing the solvent, the residue was treated with NaHCO₃ solution and filtered. The thiazolidinone (4) were crystallised from 95% ethanol (Table 3).

2-Aryl-3-[(ethoxyphenyl)-thiourido]-5-benzylidene-4 thiazolidinone (5): To EtOH (99.5%; 25 ml) was added metallic sodium (0.25 g; 0.01 M) with external cooling. After 30 min the thiazolidinone (4; 0.01 M) was added and the mixture refluxed for 5 min, followed by the addition of benzaldehyde (0.01 M) in 99% alcohol. The contents were then refluxed for 45 min, cooled, poured into water, acidified (congo red) with concentrated HCl,

filtered, and the solid was recrystallised from 95% ethanol (Table 4).

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